

Examining RCD Roles and Activities through the Lens of Facings

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Academic Research Computing and Data (RCD) as a profession remains in its formative stages. Previous efforts have been made to define, formalize, and analyze the roles within the profession. Important among those efforts is the creation of the ‘facings’ model. This study, the third in a series, is a preliminary examination of the relationships between educational background, majority facings, and the work activities of RCD professionals using data from our prior 2021 RCD workforce national survey. Findings suggest that new questions must be asked to provide details of RCD Professionals’ work scope, especially facilitator-type roles. A pivotal next step is to clearly define the knowledge, skills, and characteristics required for individuals to thrive in these positions.

CCS Concepts: • **Social and professional topics** → **Computing occupations**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: RCD, Professionalization, Facilitation, Research Computing, Workforce Development, Facings, Population Survey, Cyberinfrastructure

1 INTRODUCTION

Within the broader career paths of computing, information technology, and scientific research, Advanced Research Cyberinfrastructure Facilitator (i.e., Research Computing Facilitator, Research Facilitator) positions are still in their formative stages in comparison to other long-established professions (e.g., computer scientist, systems administrator). “Facilitator” positions require a broad mixture of technological, analytical, and research experience and knowledge combined with social-emotional skills to effectively interface with researchers and diagnose technological needs across various research domains. Reflecting the increasing importance that computing plays in advancing scientific discovery,

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53 facilitator-type positions are growing rapidly and have become integral to most research programs at major academic
54 institutions. However, despite clear demand, many such institutions face challenges in recruiting and retaining Facilitator
55 talent – these positions are not well defined, and the work activities, professional interactions, and relationships these
56 professionals engage in are poorly understood.

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58 A pivotal next step in the professionalization of research computing and data (RCD) facilitation roles is to clearly
59 define the knowledge, skills, and characteristics required for individuals to thrive in these positions. This paper is the
60 third in a series that analyzes data from the CaRCC Professionalization working group, 2021 RCD Workforce survey [6].
61 Herein, we explore the relationships, activities, and educational domains of the “Facilitator” role among other Research
62 Computing and Data Professionals (RCD Pros). We leverage data visualizations and the CaRCC Facings [1] to create
63 insights into these relationships. Drivers for this work include (1) identifying the professional development needs of
64 RCD Pros to establish environments where these professionals can thrive and (2) to enhance communication with
65 human resources professionals, university leaders, and others about the complex nature and requisite skills, experience
66 and knowledge, of facilitator positions for effective employee recruitment and retention.
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72 2 PREVIOUS WORK

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74 Seminal work began in 2014 to formalize and study the RCD profession. An NSF-funded project focused on Advanced
75 CyberInfrastructure Research and Educational Facilitation (ACI-REF) defined ACI-REFs as professionals who facilitate
76 scientists’ use of research computing (RC) resources. In addition, Michael and Maas acknowledged and explained the
77 “human” role of using RC technology as completing the cycle [7]; there is a need for CI innovators to work with
78 researchers to find new ways to leverage technology for the advancement of science.
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81 Between 2017 and 2018, a Research Coordination Network (NSF award 1148996) was established to study cyberinfras-
82 tructure more broadly, formalize key concepts, and characterize its path to becoming a profession. The idea of defining
83 what a person in research computing does by thinking about who or what they face was established as “the facings”
84 model. This original concept has now evolved into CaRCC’s five facings model[1]: systems-facing, researcher-facing,
85 software-facing, data-facing, and strategy/policy-facing. At this juncture, human resource offices within academic
86 institutions struggled to classify RCD positions as distinct from enterprise IT positions [2], especially facilitator-type
87 positions. To address this challenge and to support career advancement for RCD Pros, the RCD Professionalization
88 group created an HR Job Family Framework. Establishing the “facings” model and distinctly defined positions has
89 helped establish a national understanding of the breadth and depth of RCD (or cyberinfrastructure) positions.
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92 Researchers continue to examine various aspects of the RCD profession due to the dearth of available information
93 on this important population. Two recent studies, the characterization of the RCD workforce and RCD compensation,
94 were conducted using the data from a 2021 survey of RCD professionals from any facing. This initial survey provided
95 important baseline data that could be analyzed in various ways. The initial paper on RCD characterization reported
96 demographic information (i.e., race, gender, etc.) of those in the RCD profession, professionals’ thoughts on the RCD
97 field, and levels of job satisfaction [6]. The RCD Compensation paper focused on analyzing compensation for RCD
98 professions in academia as compared to industry positions. This study found that RCD roles, which require expertise in
99 both research and technology domains, were compensated less than the median for each domain area, research and
100 technology, respectively, as documented by the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics. [4].
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3 METHODOLOGY

Data used in this analysis was sourced from the aforementioned RCD professionals 2021 survey[5]. Details of this survey have been described previously [6] and represent 563 valid, unique responses for analysis. This data spans 175 different institutions within the US, with a larger majority being from R1 universities. For this paper, we focused on analyzing data from the survey that had not yet been explored and correlated, specifically with foundational data on the positions (e.g., the facings, education, years of experience, work activities, and job titles). Data from the following questions was extracted:

- What is the highest degree you have earned?
- Which of these best describes the field, content area, or domain of your formal education?
- For the portion of your position dedicated to RCD responsibilities: What percentage of your time is focused on each of the following areas (RCD facings)?
- Which activities do you spend at least 20% of your RCD time on? (Choose up to 5 activities that you spend the most time on)?

The de-identified dataset contained 539 responses, of which 531 contained complete data for percentage time focused on facings and were taken forward for analysis. Activity correlations were calculated as the Pearson correlation coefficient, with p-values considered significant if lower than 0.05 after Bonferroni correction. Hierarchical clustering was performed on the entire correlation matrix, with distances calculated with Ward linkage on cluster centroids. For work experience analysis, education fields with less than 10 respondents were not considered, resulting in the removal of “earth sciences” from this data. For education domain analysis, only responses with up to 3 domains were considered (526/531 responses) to reduce data-duplication during analysis.

We categorized survey participants into 6 groups - researcher-, systems-, software-, data-, strategy/policy-facing, and no majority-facing. Majority facing was defined as spending at least 50% of their time on work related to one of the 5 facings. Of these, the no majority facing comprised the largest group (45%), with researcher (20%), systems (13%), software (10%), strategy/policy (9%) and data (5%) groups following in order of decreasing size. In order to understand the relationships between facings and education and RCD-related activities, we did not use the “no majority” facings for this paper. Additional plots with this data can be found on the RCD-Nexus website. Survey results were analyzed with R version 4.3.1, corrplot 0.92 and tidyverse R packages.

4 RESULTS

We first sought to understand the educational background of the RCD workforce represented in this survey. As expected, the majority of degrees were in the fields of computer and information sciences (30%). Approximately 37% held a doctorate in their formal field of education, while only 4% did not have a bachelor’s degree. This trend was preserved when the participants were split into sub-groups based on their stated majority facing (i.e., those who spent 50% of their time focused on that RCD facing). However, for the systems-facing majority only 6% held a doctorate, while 58% listed a bachelor’s as their highest educational degree. This difference in education systems-facing roles would allow for an earlier entry point into the RCD workforce. Additional survey data or interviews would be needed to elucidate why other facings tend to have larger populations with advanced degrees.

We also looked at the proportion of total work experience within RCD to understand whether certain domains are primed to enter the RCD workforce early in their careers. The median proportion of RCD work experience was highest for the physical sciences (0.75) and engineering (0.70), and lowest for social sciences, arts and humanities (0.47).

157 However, the educational background was not a strong predictor of the types of RCD activities, such as “consulting” or
 158 “software,” that professionals spent their time on. In contrast, we observed clear relationships between some education
 159 domains and facings as shown in Figure1 (left side to center). For example, a very large proportion of life science degree
 160 holders identified as majority researcher-facing.
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162 In order to understand how RCD roles are distinct
 163 and where they overlap, we mapped the relationship of
 164 majority facing to major activities as shown in Figure1
 165 (center to right side). Largely, each majority facing is in-
 166 volved in a broad distribution of activities. There are spe-
 167 cific activities in these roles that are more well-defined
 168 than others, namely, systems-facing strongly mapped
 169 to “systems” activity, researcher-facing to “consulting,”
 170 software-facing to “software” activity, and strategy-facing
 171 to “managing,” “collab,” and “financial.” Overall this map-
 172 ping demonstrates that RCD professionals have broad
 173 roles with a wide breadth of activities and that these roles
 174 are more of a continuum from one to the other rather
 175 than discrete buckets of responsibilities.
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177 To better assess the relationship between facings and
 178 RCD-activities, we created 5 groups of RCD-activities
 179 such that activities within each group were correlated. We
 180 determined these groups empirically based on personal
 181 experiences and observations so as to provide an intuitive
 182 baseline against which to compare the survey results. The
 183 activity groups were as follows: (1) Group1: admin, report-
 184 ing, financial, project_management (2) Group2: man-
 185 aging, collab, other (3) Group3: events, communication,
 186 consulting, doc_teaching, tickets (4) Group4: research,
 187 tech_work (5) Group5: software, dev_service, systems,
 188 security.

194 As seen in Figure2, some activity-groups map fairly
 195 well to specific majority facings. For instance, Group1
 196 and Group2 map strongly onto strategy-facing, Group3
 197 to researcher-facing, Group4 to data-facing, and Group5
 198 to systems-facing. We also observe overlaps between the
 199 facings, for instance, both Group4 and Group5 map strongly onto software-facing. This suggests that the empirically
 200 determined activity-groups are a reasonable representation of the types of activities that RCD professionals engage in
 201 within the various facings, providing some validity to the concept of facings themselves. However, we also observe
 202 that there are significant overlaps in the activities between specific facings, such that thinking of facings as mutually
 203 exclusive segments would be incorrect.
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Fig. 1. Sankey plot representing respondent’s field of education (left) mapped to majority facing role (center), subsequently mapped to top five work activities respondents spent at least 20% of their time on (right). Activities are defined as [project_management] project management; [security] security/compliance; [dev_service] developing new systems, services, or solutions; [financial] budget, finance, and/or securing human, financial, or capital resources; [tech_work] performing technical work (software development, data analysis, visualization, code optimization, data management, etc.) for specific researchers; [events] community development and event planning Administrative work; [tickets] customer service/help desk/tickets; [reporting] metrics and reporting; [research] directly contributing to specific research projects intended for peer-reviewed publication Software development; [collab] partnering/collaborating with others outside your primary work unit; [communication] communications/outreach to researchers/service users; [managing] managing or supervising others; [consulting] consulting with or advising researchers; [doc_teaching] documentation and/or teaching others; [systems] system operations/administration; [other] other (write in responses)

Fig. 2. Circular barplots depicting the number of respondents who spent 20% or more time on a given activity. Each subplot comprises one majority facing. Activities are arranged clockwise according to groups defined in the text. Bar colors represent each empirical group (1-pink, 2-orange, 3-blue, 4-green, 5-purple).

Fig. 3. Pairwise activity correlation matrix for activities on which respondents spent 20% time or more. Point size and color represent the strength and direction of correlation, respectively

project_management, managing, reports, events (3) communication, consulting, doc_teaching, tickets (4) research, tech_work, software (5) dev_service, systems, security, other. Of these, cluster (3) activities showed the strongest positive relationships amongst themselves.

Our second approach was to extract only responses corresponding to a specific majority facing to reveal specific facings relationships. While some majority facings had fewer data-points, we nonetheless observed some significant associations. For example, “research”-“tech_work” for researcher-facing, “admin”-“project_management” and “research”-“software” for software-facing, “software”-“dev_service” for data-facing, “managing”-“project_management” for systems-facing, and “consulting”-“doc_teaching” for strategy-facing. These correlated pairs reveal the overlaps between activities within the different facings, but could also potentially reveal how an activity itself is understood differently by each facing. For example, “security”-“systems” was strongly correlated, as was “security”-“admin,” however “admin”-“systems” were negatively correlated. This suggests that “security” could mean a different set of component activities/tasks based on the context in which it is being considered.

More broadly, we observed that certain activity majority facing relationships are more well-defined than others. Namely, systems-facing is strongly mapped to “systems” activity, software-facing to “software” activity, and strategy-facing to “managing”, “collab” and “financial”. In contrast, researcher-facing and data-facing were less strongly mapped

In addition to looking at RCD activities mapped to a majority facing, we took a data-driven approach to reveal the activity pairs significantly correlated with each other. This allows us to compare the survey results against our empirical understanding of the activities comprising each majority facing. These activity-pair correlations were then organized into five hierarchical clusters to identify groups of correlated activities. Most correlations were quite weak, which is expected since the data consisted of several different sub-groups, which might differ in their activity correlations.

To strengthen the relationships between activity-pairs, we took two approaches. First, we increased the threshold of percent time spent in any facing from 50% to 85%. This revealed strong positive correlations between some activities, resulting in the identification of 5 activity clusters as follows (Figure3): (1) admin, financial (2) collab,

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261 onto specific activities. This might indicate that some facings require a much broader set of activities and skill sets.
 262 Alternatively, it could indicate that these facings are less well-understood or well-defined for the general RCD workforce.
 263 We qualify these findings due to the limitations of the current dataset because of small sample sizes and unequal
 264 representation of different majority facings within the responses collected.
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267 5 CONCLUSION

268 Research computing is a dynamic environment that is constantly evolving. This includes the human element, rcd-
 269 facilitator positions. During the few years since the preliminary survey, there have been advancements in the field,
 270 and the analysis of the impacts of these changes is warranted. For example, as reflected in the initial survey results,
 271 “research” is primarily included in official job titles for those in data-, researcher-, and strategy-facings. The “research”
 272 moniker was initially important to distinguish between RCD and enterprise IT roles. With the rise of RC needs to
 273 advance both science and classroom learning, examining if the use of “research” in job titles has faded over time can
 274 provide valuable insights. Further, in earlier stages of the RCD profession, facilitators supported researchers from
 275 their educational domain (e.g., a facilitator with a psychology background supported the Social Sciences). Facilitators
 276 used domain expertise to “translate” domain-related research objectives into high-end computing needs/solutions [3].
 277 However, as tools and technologies continue advancing, evidence is needed to determine if the trend is domain agnostic,
 278 with the importance focused on the expertise needed in the newest technologies.
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281 Surveying those in RCD roles, especially facilitator-type positions, on a regular cadence is required to (1) identify
 282 trends, (2) observe the profession and roles under varying lenses, and (3) represent the community and its impact. The
 283 2021 survey is preliminary and could not uncover all patterns. A future study can address critical gaps.
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287 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

288 The authors thank Lauren Michael for reviewing and editing this paper. We also thank RCD Professionalization Working
 289 Group members Deb McCaffrey and Levi Dolan. This work is supported by the RCD-Nexus grant OAC-2100003 from
 290 the National Science Foundation.
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